

Assessing Technical Efficiency in Public institutions: Evidences from Local Government Authorities in Tanzania.

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Abstract— the aim of the study was to assess technical efficiency of local government authorities in Tanzania. The study examines the ability of the local authorities in allocating available resource efficiently in the production of output measure by internal revenue generated from local sources. The study used data envelopment analysis (DEA) in estimating the relative efficiency score of the local authorities. The findings of the study show that on average Local government authorities in Tanzania are relatively inefficient hence need to improve in the use of resources and increase the internal revenue generation, hence decrease their dependence to grants and donations from central government and donors. The results also show that scale efficiency was higher than pure technical efficiency for district councils and town council suggesting that the sources of inefficiency is managerial related problems, hence calling improvement in resource management, allocation and decision marking in order to increase their relative efficiencies.

Key Words: Efficiency, Data Envelopment Analysis, Local Government Authorities, Public Institutions, Tanzania

I. INTRODUCTION

Public sector organizations are the state/government owned organizations which are responsible for production, ownership, sale, provision, delivery or allocation of goods and services to the government or its citizens. It includes all publicly controlled or publicly funded agencies and other entities that deliver public programs, goods or services (Dude & Danescu, 2011). Performance in public sector organizations is among the key issues of concern in the global economy especially in the developing countries which still depend on developing assistance from developed countries, donors and developing agencies (Fountain, 2001). Most development assistance no longer provide funds to the developing countries on the basis of soundness of the project funded, they rather require an overall soundness of public sector which would enhance national economic competitiveness with high ability to manage public expenditure with care at all stages of the business cycle. According to Picciotto (1998), developing assistance requires high ability of public sector organizations to establish processes which screen out dubious schemes before they are undertaken in order to reduce losses and failure rates and also improve the quality of public expenditure which in turn would improve the return from investment projects involving the state as a source of funds or of sovereign guarantee. Apart from external factors, public sector has recently experienced internal environmental, technological and operational changes which have resulted into increased demand for better and quality services and products from all public sector stakeholders (Dixit (2002). With decreasing donor support, governments in developing countries have experienced inside push to manage operating costs in public organizations, decrease in tax burden to the citizen and improved revenue collections from other sources while ensuring transparency and accountability in all public sector organization (Grote, 2000).

In Tanzania Public sector organizations include government ministries, departments, agencies, local government authorities and other organizations owned or controlled by the government or citizens of Tanzania. Since independence in 1961, the government of Tanzania was directly involved in delivering of both core and noncore public services such as education, health, water, sanitation and other public services. The primary goal was to improve service provisions to the society efficiently and effectively and to ensure value for money. The government

of Tanzania faced challenges on balancing activities between planning, creating and delivery of high value products and services to the society while minimizing costs whenever possible (URT, 2003). There was also increased bureaucracy in the services provision, increased political interference, lack of innovation and lack of transparency and accountability which together contributed to the poor performance of public sector as a whole especially on service delivery to the society. This resulted in the decision by the government of Tanzania to undertake public sector reforms which started in 1980s with the primary aim of improving service delivery, transparency and accountability in public sector. Among the major reforms in the public sector service delivery in Tanzania was the formation and implementation of Local government reform programme in 1998 with the aim of transferring resources from central to Local government and devolving and decentralizing power to create more autonomous Local Government Authorities. The main long-term goal of LGRP was to contribute to the Government's efforts of reducing the proportion of Tanzanians living in poverty so as to improve quality, access and equitable delivery of public services, particularly to the poor.

Although the central government have since then strived to ensure independence and growth in local government authorities as the major service delivery wing to the citizens, the LGAs have not been much successful around the country. The operations of Local government Authorities have been reported to be poor mainly due to high dependence in central government, inefficiency use of available resources and inability of LGAs to deliver value for money as expected (NAO, 2013, 2014). Studies conducted in country on Local government authorities have mainly focused on performance of individual local government authorities in the country in which results shows unsatisfactory performance (Mzenzi, 2013, Frelstad et al, 2008). Evidences on how efficient are the Local government authorities in the country are not yet known. Since, the institutions use public funds they are required to use them efficiently when delivering the services to the citizens. This study therefore focuses on technical efficiency of local government authorities in Tanzania by looking the efficiency use of resources to mobilize internal funds which are important for service delivery and independence of the local government authorities.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Efficiency is among an important performance measures for any government which seek to determine to what extent the government achieved its goals. It involves maximizing outputs such as the volume of services provided, minimizing inputs such as the amount of resources or capital required to produce those services and maintaining or improving quality. According to WCER (2004) efficiency government or public organizations can be described as “achieving the maximum outputs from a given level of resources used to carry out an activity”. It is therefore the relationship between outputs, in terms of goods, services or other results and resources used to produce them. Government efficiency can also be defined as the optimal employment of resources over time which can be used as a measure for government to examine how well it is performing the tasks it is supposed to do within a given time frame, without any regard of whether the right things are being done (Abedian & Biggs, 1998). Efficiency in public sector can also be defined by integrating it with quality hence as the best use of resources available for provision of public services. This can be done by lowering inputs in terms of money, people, asset etc while maintaining output at constant level or by keeping inputs constant while increasing the level of output or improved services (Farrell, 1957).

From economic perspectives, the concept of efficiency can be categorized into three categories, the technical efficiency, allocative efficiency and dynamic efficiency (Worthington & Dolley, 2000). Technical efficiency refers to the use of productive resources in the most technologically efficient manner hence deriving the maximum possible output from the given set of inputs (Coelli et al 1998, Somanathan et al, 2000). In public organizations which offer services to the community without profit motive, technical efficiency means improvement in service output given constant level of resources or production of the constant level services using fewer resources (Peacock et al, 2001). Allocative efficiency refers to the distribution of productive resources among different alternative uses in order to produce the optimal mix of output. Hence allocative efficiency is about making choice between different combinations in order to deliver the optimal mix of output in the organizations. The combinations of technical efficiency and allocative efficiency results into total economic efficiency of any given firm (Peacock et al, 2001). The dynamic efficient on the other hand refers to the economic efficiency in the use of scarce resources at a given time hence reflect both allocative efficiency and technical efficiency. In public organization, activities or services offered would be considered as economically efficient is there is no alternative use of the resources that would yield a higher value or benefit.

In public institutions such as local government authorities efficiency is among the important determinants of aggregate economic performance. The need for efficiency is such organization is very high first because they use public funds which are scarce hence need efficient allocation among different needs. Second, since the local government authorities as in most of public organization do not focus on profit making, most of financial performance measures that are used in profit oriented firms are not applicable, hence efficiency measurement is an important financial performance measure for such institutions. Third, most of the governments in developing country have been donor dependent for long time for the funds to meet their developing goals and government operational goals. With the current donor trends, public sector

efficiency is among the key assessment criteria for the provision of such financing to both the central and local governments around the world (Fountain, 2001, Picciotto 1998). Fourth, there is increasing awareness among the citizens in most of developing country which now require more efficient use of the public funds, more openness in decision making, more accountability for the public funds as well as increased government responsibility to the public development. Lastly, due to the poverty level in most of developing country, policy makers recognize the importance of local government authorities' efficiency as the decision marking units, hence requesting the efficiency use of public funds when offering services to the community. With all of these, local government authorities are required to operate with high efficiency level by allocating well the scarce resources hence improve the service delivery performance and economic growth of the entire nations.

Empirical studies on public sector efficiency have reported mixed findings basing on different services provided to the community. The study by Althin & Behrenz (2004) investigated technical efficiency of Swedish government employment agency using data envelopment analysis. The study reported high average efficiency of about 70% which was found to increase with the number of unemployed and vacancies in public sector. Such findings in the country were contrary to other previous studies but which focused on efficiency of public institutions offering insurance services. These studies by Bjurek et al (1990) and Kumbhakar & Hjalmarsson (1995) reported high technical inefficiencies among the public insurance institutions in that country. Studies on public institutions offering education services have also reported presence of high inefficiencies among the institutions. The study by Jarasuriya & Woodon (2002) reported presence of high inefficiencies in different countries especially African countries such as Malawi, Zambia, Mozambique, Ethiopia, Niger and Bukina Faso. The studies by Banker et al (2004) and Grosskopf et al (2001) evaluated technical, allocative and cost efficiency of schools in USA. The Banker's results indicated presence of high technical inefficiency which increased over time while the allocative efficiency was found to be stable. On the other hand, the Grosskopf's results reported low technical efficiency in schools and countries with high proportional of home owners, highly educated individual household and the age of children. Likewise the study by Mancebon & Muniz (2008) on cost efficiency of public education institutions reported high inefficiency of public schools as compared to private schools.

Evidences from public libraries in America also report high inefficiencies whose source are technical in nature due to exceedingly long opening hours of the libraries which attracts more operating costs (Vitaliano, 1998). These results were later challenged by Hemmeter (2006) study which compared the efficiency level of public services institutions offering library services and private ones. The findings of the study reported presence of more inefficiency in private libraries as compared to public libraries. In public health institutions, the study by Athanassopoulous & Gounaris (2001) reported high inefficiency level in public hospitals operating in Greece. The findings were also supported by Farsi et al (2005) which reported high technical inefficiency in public health organization in USA.

Empirical studies on efficiency of local authorizes around the world have also reported mixed findings especially when

local authorities in developing countries are compared to those from developed countries. Among the studies conducted in developing countries include the study by Hayes & Chang (1990) in US municipalities which tested cost efficiency differences among city managers and mayor councils. The study reported an average of 80% level of efficiency while mayor councils were found to have higher average efficiency level as compare do city manager type of councils. These results indicated low inefficiency level of less that 20% among the municipalities and which could be improved in the future. Eeckaut et al (1993) also assessed the cost efficiency of Belgian municipalities, the findings indicated mean efficiency scores of between 57% to 94% among the municipalities. This implied that the level of inefficiency was between 6% to 43% hence input resources could be reduced to such extent and yet municipalities could have been able to produce the same output. The study by Niesward & Seifert (2011) also supported presence of high inefficiency among the local government authorizes, as well as the studies by Chen et al (2011) in local municipals in China, Study by Afonso & Fernandes (2008) in Portuguese municipalities as well as the study by De Borger and Kerstens (1996) in Belgian local governments.

III. METHODOLOGY

This study used data envelopment analysis model (DEA), to measure the relative efficiency of local government authorities in Tanzania. DEA model was chosen due to number of reasons, first public sector organization are characterized by use of multiple inputs and production of multiple outputs in terms of financial and social values. DEA model unlike parametric models such as stochastic frontier analysis (SFA) allows the use of multiple input and output hence DEA was most appropriate for this study. Second, most of parametric and econometric model requires the expression of function form in evaluation of efficiency in any decision making units, DEA in contrary does not require the expression of function form or estimation of error terms (Drake & Hall, 2003), hence appropriate in nonprofit institutions such as local government authorities. Third, Most of parametric models requires presence of prices for the input and output variables which are to be used in the estimation of efficiency, DEA model in contrary does not require the prices of input and output which make it appropriate for public sector institutions such as local government authorities since the prices for most of public services and products cannot be obtained at open market or be estimated with precision (Ruggiero, 2005). Lastly, DEA model does not estimate absolute efficiency of firms rather it estimates the relative efficiency of firms by comparing all other firms to the best performing firms. Due to the fact that local government authorities in Tanzania have different size, different level of services as well as political motives, DEA was found to be appropriate comparing the efficiency within the authorities.

The use of DEA was also supported by several empirical studies in public sector and nonprofit organization which also applied the model in assessing the efficiency of organs of the government in different countries. DEA model was used for assessing efficiency of Microfinance Institutions which are nonprofit organization in nature in different countries (Kipesha, 2013, Nieto et al, 2009, Nghiem et al 2006), DEA model was used to estimate efficiency of public hospitals in different countries (Athanasopoulos and Gounaris, 2001, Farsi et al, 2005), DEA model was used to measure the efficiency of governments in different countries (Baraguel-Coll et al, 2007,

Niesward and Seifert, 2011, Hauner, 2008), DEA was used to measure efficiency of public universities and schools in different countries (Kipesha and Msigwa, 2013, Grosskopf et al, 2001, Muncebon & Muniz, 2008, Mizala et al, 2002). Likewise, DEA model was used to measure the efficiency of local government authorities in different studies such as Worthington (2000) in Australian municipalities, Prieto and Zofio (2001) in Spanish Municipalities, Balaguer et al, (2002) in Spain municipalities, Afonso and Fernandes (2006) in Portuguese municipalities and Loikkanen and Susiluoto (2005) in Finland municipalities.

The technical efficiency of Local government authorities was estimated using both constant return to scale (CCR-model) as proposed by Charnes et al (1978) and variable return to scale efficiency using BCC model proposed by Banker et al (1984). The study estimate efficiency under input orientation in order to determine the input and output amounts that should be reduced or generated by the respective local government authority in order to improve their efficiency. The input oriented model was selected with assumption that it is easy for local government authorities to control the input resources that the output due to the nature of their operations.

To present the efficiency model used in this study, consider K decision units which represent respective local government authorities, which use N inputs to produce M outputs. If we denote inputs as x_{jk} ($j= 1, \dots, N$) and outputs as y_{ik} ($i=1, \dots, M$) for each local government authority k ($k=1, \dots, K$). Using the Coelli, (1998) we can express output oriented technical efficiency model as

$$MinTE = \sum_{i=1}^m (u_i y_{is}) \div \sum_{j=1}^n (v_j x_{jk}) \text{----- (i)}$$

$$Subject.to = \sum_{i=1}^m (u_i y_{ir} - y_{iF} + W \geq 0) \text{----- (ii)}$$

$$x_{jr} - \sum_{j=1}^n (u_i x_{jk} \geq 0) \text{----- (iii)}$$

$$u_j v_i \geq 0, r = 1, \dots, K$$

Where y_{ik} is the quantity of input produced by the k th DMU, x_{jk} is the quantity of j th input used by the n th DMU, u_i and v_j are the output and input weights respectively. In the above model, if $W = 0$ the efficiency measure is technical efficiency under constant return to scale (CRS) and if W is used unconstrained then it changes to variable return to scale hence estimating pure technical efficiency (Coelli, 1998).

The study used three input variables and one output variable in measuring technical efficiency of the local government authorities in Tanzania. The technical efficiency was used to measure the level of efficiency in the use of resources available in generating internal revenue which is very important for LGAs independence and meeting of its objectives. The choice of variables is among the major problem in efficiency estimation in both for profit and nonprofit organizations. This is due to the fact that, there are no standard variables that can be used for efficiency estimations. Different studies which have dealt with efficiency estimation in public sector have used different types of variables depending on the nature of institutions reviewed and data availability. Among the recent studies in local government efficiency, Loikkanen and Susiluoto (2005) used DEA with total expenditure as the input variable and a number of output variables such as children’s day care, children’s family care, open basic health care, Dental

care etc. Afonso and Fernandes (2006) used DEA with single input variable which is the total per capital expenditure and several output variables grouped into general administrative performance, education, social services, cultural services, domestic waste collection and environment protection. Balaguer et al (2002) used DEA in Spain municipalities with total expenditure as input variable and number of lighting points, total population, towns of waste collected, street infrastructure surface area, registered surface area of public parks and number of votes. Prieto and Zofio (2001) used DEA in Spanish municipalities with budgetary expenditure as the only input variable while output variables were potable water, domestic waste collection, road surface area, lighting street points, cultural and sportive infrastructures. On the other hand, Worthington measured cost efficiency of local government authorities in Australia in which input variables were number of full time workers, financial expenditure and other expenditure, the output variables were total population, number of properties acquired, portable water, domestic waste collection, rural and urban roads. Athanassopoulos and Triantis (1998) used DEA in Greek local government authorities with total current expenditure as the input variable and number of resident families, average residential area, building area, industrial and tourism area as the output variables.

Most of the studies of LGAs efficiency have been conducted in developing countries as reviewed above hence the variables selected relates with the level of economic and social development of the given area. Due to the nature and development level of Tanzania we could not adopt most of these variables as input and output since it is difficult to measure and difficult to obtain the required data. Some of the variables used in the previous studies such as infrastructure development does not measure the actual performance of LGAs in Tanzania as most of them depend of development grants from central government for development activities hence have no control on the availability of funds and budgets for capital development. Given the unstandardized nature of variables used in efficiency and due to the nature of LGAs in Tanzania, this study used three input variables and one output variables. The input variables used were population of LGA, total recurrent expenditure and development expenditure while the output variable was the revenue collected from internal sources. The choice of the variables was based on the fact that, in order for LGAs to meet their objectives of serving well the citizens, developing infrastructure etc they need to be self-independent by generating enough internal revenue which will cuter for their need instead of depending on central government and other donor grants. In Tanzania, most of LGAs projects are not conducted on time or do not finish on time due to highly dependences of LGAs to central government and donor grants which always do not come on time and again come with several conditions. Hence, LGAs are required to use their available resources to generate enough revenue from its own resources. With this view, LGA performance in all aspect depends on the extent to which such LGA can generate its own internal revenue. The internal revenue generated was therefore used as the only output variable in this model. On the other hand, to generate internal revenue, LGAs need resources, such resources depends on the nature of revenue to be generated. The study used population of the LGAs with assumption that LGA with higher population have more economic activities hence more sources of revenue to LGAs, the second input variable was recurrent expenditure which indicates the

resources used by LGAs in daily operations including offering services community, which in turn brings in revenue to the LGA. The third input variable is the development expenditure which is used as the proxy measure for capital invested by LGAs which in turn enable it to generate revenue from different investments done.

IV. RESULTS

The study examined technical efficiency of local government authorities in Tanzania. The efficiency results indicates that only 3 LGAs were relatively efficient under constant return to scale in 2011 and 6 LGAs in 2012 and 2013. Under variable return to scale, a total of 11, 13 and 10 LGAs were relatively efficient in the three years of operations. The average technical efficiency results of LGAs in Tanzania were very low. This implies that, most of LGAs reviewed were relatively inefficient in the production of output in terms of internal revenue mobilization using the available resources. The results show that the efficient LGAs under constant return to scales were only 4.8% of the total LGAs reviewed; hence 95.2% were relatively inefficient. The average technical efficiency scores were 30.7%, 39% and 36.03% for 2011 to 2013 respectively. This indicates that on average the LGAs were supposed to use less 40% of their input resources to produce the output level that was produced in the three years. This also implies that the level of inefficiency in LGAs is more that 60% in the use of input resources they receive to produce the output measured by the internal revenue mobilized.

Table 1: Average Technical Efficiency Results

	2011	2012	2013
Number of Firms	63	63	63
Number of Efficient MFIs (CRS)	3	6	6
Number of Efficient MFIs (VRS)	11	13	10
Average Technical Efficiency (CRS)	0.3071	0.3898	0.3603
Average Pure Tech. Efficiency (VRS)	0.5275	0.5960	0.6457
Average Scale Efficiency	0.5281	0.6181	0.5293

The average relative efficiency results under pure technical efficiency (VRS) were 52.75%, 59.6% and 64.57% for the three years respectively. This implies that under pure technical environments the LGAs reviewed were supposed to use less than 65% on average of the input resources used, to produce the same level of output. In other words, the LGAs were supposed to use fewer resources in terms of recurrent funds, development funds and available potential population to mobilize the same level of internal revenue collected. Hence, there is revenue collection inefficiency of about 35% in average among the LGAs reviewed.

The average results under scale efficiency were 52.81%, 61.81% and 52.93% for the three years respectively. This indicate the extent to which LGAs have been able use their input efficiency in the production of output in comparison to the most productive scale level. The results shows that the LGAs review in average have diverged from the most productive scales by 47.19%, 38.19% and 47.07% for the three years respectively. This implies that, most of the LGAs reviewed have a chance to improve their productive efficiency by reducing inefficiency and producing output at the most productive scale level. The average scale efficiency was found to be higher than pure technical efficiency in the most of the years reviewed; this implies that most of LGA’s inefficiency

was due to inappropriate allocation of resources as well as operating in inappropriate scale.

The results on return to scale also support the possibility of the LGAs reviewed to improve their technical efficiency level in the internal revenue collection. The results show that in 2011, 4.76% of the LGAs reviewed were operating under constant return to scale, these LGAs were producing own source revenue at the most productive scales for the period. The results are presented in table 2 below

Table 2: LGAs Return to Scale Results

	CRS		IRS		DRS		Total	
	LGAs	%	LGAs	%	LGAs	%	LGAs	%
2011	3	4.76	58	92.06	2	3.17	63	100
2012	6	9.52	56	88.89	1	1.59	63	100
2013	4	6.35	58	92.06	1	1.59	63	100

On the other hand, 92.6% of the 63 LGAs reviewed were producing at increasing return to scale, this implies that although such LGAs were relatively inefficiency but their possibility that in the future they can mobilize more internal source revenue using minimum resources hence improve their relative efficiency. The remaining 3.17% of the LGAs reviewed were found to operate at decreasing rate to scale, this implies that if there no necessary effort to improve their efficiency in the revenue collection, such LGAs are expected to have declining relative efficiency in the future.

The efficiency of LGAs in Tanzania was also assessed based on the type of Local government authority. Depending on the size, position and functions, LGAs can be grouped into three groups, the district councils (DC), the municipal councils (MC) and town councils (TC). The average technical results are shown in the table below.

Table 3: Average Technical Efficiency by LGAs Type

		2011	2012	2013
District Council	CRS	0.2440	0.3038	0.2658
	VRS	0.4779	0.5394	0.5978
	SCALE	0.4696	0.5524	0.4442
Municipal Council	CRS	0.6367	0.8012	0.7980
	VRS	0.7482	0.8291	0.8357
	SCALE	0.8527	0.9563	0.9398
Town Council	CRS	0.2679	0.5264	0.5804
	VRS	0.6890	0.8726	0.9161
	SCALE	0.3961	0.6020	0.6448

Technical efficiency results under constant return to scale average scores of 24.4%, 30.38% and 26.58% for district councils for the three years respectively. The average technical efficiency results under constant return to scale (CRS) for municipal councils were 63.67%, 80.12% and 79.8% for the three years respectively, while the results for town councils were 26.79%, 52.64% and 58.04% for the three years respectively. The technical efficiency results under constant return to scale shows highly inefficiency in the internal revenue collection among the districts councils and town councils. The results show that district council were operating with more than 70% inefficiency as they used more input resource and produced little output as compared to the best performers. Likewise, the town councils were found to require an average

45% of the input used to produce the same level of output in the internal revenue mobilization for the three years. The municipal councils were found to be more relatively efficient than the DC and TC. Municipal councils were found to require more than 70% of the input they have used to produce the same level of output. This indicates that although in average municipal councils were not efficient, but the level of inefficient was less than 30% as compared to DC and TC.

The average technical efficiency results by LGAs type shows that pure technical efficiency results under variable return to scale are higher than scale efficiency for district councils and town councils. This implies that the inefficiencies observed in LGAs which are district councils are due to management related issues. Hence, poor management of resources, poor decision making regarding the input resources and all other management related problem contributes to the poor internal revenue mobilization in such LGAs. On the other hand, the average pure technical efficiency results for municipal councils were found to be lower than the average scale efficiencies in the three years of review. This indicates that the little inefficiency level observed in municipal councils in the use of resources to produce output measure by local revenue mobilized are all due to technical issue which are out of management control.

The technical efficiency results were also analyzed basing on the regions in which LGAs operate. This was done in order to ascertain whether the location of LGA count of the efficiency level as well as to make comparison on efficiency score among the ten regions included in the study. The results on average technical efficiency basing of regions are summarized in the table below.

Table 4: Average Technical Efficiency by Regions

Region	RTS	2011	2012	2013	Average	Rank
Dsm	CRS	0.7918	0.8315	0.949	0.8576	1
Tabora	CRS	0.5242	0.5278	0.47	0.5073	2
Pwani	CRS	0.2651	0.4364	0.499	0.4001	3
Arusha	CRS	0.2892	0.4915	0.351	0.3772	4
Mbeya	CRS	0.3026	0.3418	0.366	0.3366	5
KLM	CRS	0.2381	0.4169	0.351	0.3352	6
Moro	CRS	0.3562	0.3075	0.257	0.3068	7
Tanga	CRS	0.2887	0.271	0.232	0.2638	8
Dodoma	CRS	0.1519	0.3281	0.289	0.2562	9
Mwanza	CRS	0.1006	0.1975	0.14	0.1461	10

The findings of the study indicates that Dar-es-alaam has the highest average technical efficiency score of 85.76% followed by Tabora region with the average 50.73%, Pwani (40.01%), Arusha (37.72%), Mbeya (33.66%), Kilimanjaro (33.52%), Morogoro (30.68%), Tanga (26.38%), Dodoma (25.62%) and the last one is Mwanza with an average technical efficiency score of 14.61%. The average technical efficiency scores shows high inefficiency level of more than 50% for the most regions reviewed. The findings show that while Dar-es-salaam used an excess of 14.4% of the input resources to generate the same level of output which is the internal revenue collected, Mwanza, Dodoma, Tanga, Morogoro, Kilimanjaro, Mbeya, Arusha and Pwani needed less than 50% of the average input resources that they have used in the three years to generate the same level of internal revenue mobilized. The results also indicates that, the regions reviewed have enough

resources that can be used to increase internal revenue collection, the management of the regions should take necessary measures to improve internal revenue collections in their regions.

The analysis of the individual local government authorities in the regions indicates that in some regions there was no LGAs which were in the efficient frontier line, while in some regions, some LGAs were among the efficient decision making units. The results on the number of efficient LGAs in regions reviewed are presented in the table below.

Table 5: Number of Efficient LGAs in Regions Reviewed

		2011	2012	2013
Arusha	No. LGA	6	6	6
	Efficient	0%	17%	0%
Dodoma	No. LGA	6	6	6
	Efficient	0%	17%	17%
DSM	No. LGA	3	3	3
	Efficient	33.3%	67%	67%
Kilimanjaro	No. LGA	7	7	7
	Efficient	0%	14.3%	14.3%
Mbeya	No. LGA	8	8	8
	Efficient	12.5%	0%	0%
Morogoro	No. LGA	6	6	6
	Efficient	16.7%	0%	0%
Mwanza	No. LGA	5	5	5
	Efficient	0%	0%	0%
Pwani	No. LGA	7	7	7
	Efficient	0%	0%	0%
Tabora	No. LGA	6	6	6
	Efficient	0%	17%	0%
Tanga	No. LGA	9	9	9
	Efficient	0%	0%	0%

The findings shows that in the six LGAs sampled from Arusha region, only 17% were efficient in 2012 while there was no efficient LGA in the other two years of review. The sample included six LGAs from Dodoma region, out of that 17% were efficient in 2012 and 2013 while the remaining 83% were technically inefficient. The results from Tanga, Pwani and Mwanza indicated that there was no efficient LGA in the three years of review, while Mbeya, Tabora and Morogoro had some LGAs in the efficient frontier line in one of the three years. The results show that, Dar-es-salaam region was the best performer as among the three LGAs samples, 67% were relatively efficient as compared to the total LGAs sample in this study.

Efficiency results on individual LGAs (Appendix 1) show that, in 2011 a total of three LGAs were relatively efficient. These LGAs included Mbeya Municipal council, Mvomero district council and Temeke municipal council. These councils were found to be relatively efficient in the use of input resources to generate the output measured by the amount of internal revenue generated. This indicates the high ability of these LGAs to be independent of the donors and government as they can generate their own local revenue at relatively high amount as compared to other LGAs in that year. The results also show that, in 2011 worst performing LGAs in terms of using input resources to mobilize internal revenue were Kilindi district council in Tanga (3.53%), Misungwi district council in Mwanza (4.52%), Same district council in Kilimanjaro

(6.87%), Mpwapwa district council in Dodoma (6.97%) and Moshi district council in Kilimanjaro (7.37%).

The efficiency scores for individual LGAs in 2012 show that six LGAs were in the efficient frontier line; these include Temeke MC, Ilala MC, Urambo DC, Siha DC, Arusha MC and Dodoma MC. This implies that only Temeke MC was able to maintain its level of technical efficient in 2012 while other two efficient LGAs in 2011 were unable to maintain their level of efficiency in 2012. On the other hand, the results show that, the five poor performing LGAs in 2012 were Kilindi DC, Morogoro DC, Hahi DC, Mwanza DC and Kilosa DC with average inefficiency level of about 98% in the internal revenue collection level. In the third year of review, the number of efficient LGAs declined to four, which included Temeke MC, Dodoma MC, Moshi MC and Kinondoni MC. On the other hand, the last poor performing LGAs were Bahi DC, Morogoro DC, Kilosa DC, Mpwapwa DC and Sengerema DC with an average inefficiency level of more than 98% on internal revenue collection using the available resources.

V. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The aim of the study was to examine technical efficiency level of local government authorities in Tanzania in the internal revenue mobilization. The study was conducted in Tanzania in which a total of 10 regions and 63 local government authorities were included in the sample study. The technical efficiency of local government authorities in Tanzania was measured using Data envelopment analysis with the aim of assess the extent to which LGAs are able to use well their inputs in production of outputs. In order for LGA to be independent in need to reduce its independence on central government hence we assessed the efficiency to which LGAs can use available resources to generate output in terms of local revenue collection.

The results on technical efficiency show that on average LGA's in Tanzania are relatively inefficiency as they do not use well the inputs to produce the output. The average technical efficiency scores were 30% to 39% for three years' time which indicate high average inefficiency level of about 60% among LGAs reviewed. This is an indication that LGAs in Tanzania in general do not mobilize enough internal revenue which could reduce their independence on central Government grants and subsidies. The findings of the study also shows that on average LGAs in Tanzania have diverged from the most productive scales by 45% on average which means that in future there is possibility of improvement if at all they decide to do so. The results of scale efficiency in general were found to be higher than pure technical efficiency scores which suggest that most of inefficiency observed were not caused by managerial decisions rather were due to operating in inappropriate scale and inappropriate allocation of resources which might be contributed by political factors.

The results obtained on LGAs technical efficiency level support most of the previous studies which also show that LGAs around the world are not technically efficient. The findings of the study were in-line with studies by Niesward and Seifert (2011) which report presences of spending inefficiencies among Local government authorities, Chen et al (2011) which report high inefficiency in local municipals in China as well as the studies by De Borger and Kerstens (1996) and the study by Afonso and Fernandes (2008) which all report high spending inefficiency among government sectors. Apart from studies which focus on municipal councils, others studies from other public sector organization have also indicated

presence of high inefficiencies among these institutions. The study by Doble (1995) in United states, Deprins et al (1984) in Belgium, and Borenstein et al (2004) in Brazil all reported high relative inefficiencies among the public institutions which offer postal services. On the other hand, the findings on this study were contrary to some findings in public sector organization which reported presence of high efficiency among public institutions in different countries. The study by Althin and Behrenz (2004) investigated technical efficiency of Swedish Government employment agency using DEA and reported presence of high average technical efficiency.

The findings of our study also shows presence of different efficiency levels among LGAs and across all type of LGAs both district council, municipal council and town council. The results show average technical efficiency level for district council was found to range between 24% to 31%, town council between 26% to 58% while municipal councils which performed between it ranges between 63% to 79%. The finding show that the source of inefficiency for both district councils and town councils was related to managerial issues, that is the poor management which fails to monitor and allocate well the resources since pure technical efficiency was higher than scare efficiency. The findings for municipal council was different, the scare efficiency was higher than pure technical efficiency suggesting that the level of inefficiency observed was technical in nature and not managerial related. The findings of the study also support many empirical findings in public sector which also witness poor efficiency level among the public spending organizations across the world. Some of these include Vitaliano (1998) which also which also found high inefficiency among public libraries in New York and the source of such inefficiency was technical in nature as in municipal councils in our results. The study results also support the findings on technical efficiency among public health institutions which also indicates presence of high technical inefficiency among public institutions around the world (Athanassopoulos and Gounaris, 2001, Farsi et al, 2005, Tovar and Cejas, 2010).

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Appendix 1: Local Government Authorities Technical Efficiency Results

NO	DMU	2011				2012				2013			
		CRS	VRS	SE	RTS	CRS	VRS	SE	RTS	CRS	VRS	SE	RTS
1	Arusha DC	0.3896	0.4744	0.8213	irs	0.4797	0.4916	0.9757	irs	0.2351	0.4590	0.5122	irs
2	Arusha MC	0.5182	0.5737	0.9032	irs	1	1	1	crs	0.6801	0.6807	0.9991	irs
3	Bagamoyo DC	0.2438	0.3749	0.6502	irs	0.2674	0.4091	0.6537	irs	0.3180	0.3636	0.8744	irs
4	Bahi DC	0.1419	0.8080	0.1756	irs	0.0961	0.5272	0.1822	irs	0.0642	0.7221	0.0889	irs
5	Chamwino DC	0.1100	0.3552	0.3096	irs	0.2984	1	0.2984	irs	0.1368	0.6258	0.2186	irs
6	Chunya DC	0.1946	0.5350	0.3638	irs	0.6477	0.8404	0.7707	irs	0.5006	0.6196	0.8080	irs
7	Dodoma MC	0.3929	0.4013	0.9790	irs	1	1	1	crs	1	1	1	crs
8	Hai DC	0.1337	0.3172	0.4216	irs	0.4165	0.5289	0.7874	irs	0.3016	0.6745	0.4471	irs
9	Handeni DC	0.1092	0.3147	0.3470	irs	0.1821	0.4147	0.4392	irs	0.1011	0.5326	0.1898	irs
10	Igunga DC	0.8902	1	0.8902	irs	0.2327	0.4229	0.5504	irs	0.1626	0.6230	0.2610	irs
11	Ilala MC	0.7337	1	0.7337	drs	1	1	1	crs	0.8481	0.8534	0.9938	irs
12	Ileje DC	0.1750	0.5336	0.3279	irs	0.2202	0.6396	0.3443	irs	0.2158	0.9338	0.2311	irs
13	Karatu DC	0.1839	0.4052	0.4538	irs	0.3321	0.4798	0.6921	irs	0.2914	0.8058	0.3616	irs
14	Kibaha DC	0.1378	0.6826	0.2018	irs	0.7604	1	0.7604	irs	0.8123	1	0.8123	irs
15	Kibaha TC	0.3059	0.6322	0.4839	irs	0.6438	0.8809	0.7308	irs	0.7818	0.8749	0.8936	irs
16	Kilindi DC	0.0353	1	0.0353	irs	0.0778	1	0.0778	irs	0.0995	0.7662	0.1299	irs
17	Kilombero DC	0.3189	0.4222	0.7552	irs	0.5578	0.6179	0.9027	irs	0.4510	0.5719	0.7886	irs
18	Kilosa DC	0.0815	0.2471	0.3296	irs	0.1159	0.3362	0.3447	irs	0.0701	0.3358	0.2088	irs
19	Kinondoni MC	0.6416	1	0.6416	drs	0.4946	0.5103	0.9693	drs	1	1	1	crs
20	Kisarawe DC	0.1412	0.5430	0.2601	irs	0.2299	0.8506	0.2702	irs	0.4218	0.8005	0.5269	irs
21	Kondoa DC	0.1217	0.2645	0.4602	irs	0.2214	0.3101	0.7140	irs	0.2150	0.3490	0.6162	irs
22	Kongwa DC	0.0751	0.3134	0.2398	irs	0.2223	0.4430	0.5019	irs	0.2374	0.4882	0.4863	irs
23	Korogwe DC	0.1121	0.3096	0.3621	irs	0.1202	0.2929	0.4104	irs	0.1056	0.6550	0.1612	irs
24	Korogwe TC	0.2300	0.7459	0.3083	irs	0.4091	0.8643	0.4733	irs	0.3791	0.9573	0.3960	irs
25	Kwimba DC	0.0934	0.2495	0.3745	irs	0.1582	0.2936	0.5390	irs	0.1062	0.2744	0.3868	irs
26	Kyela DC	0.1508	0.3283	0.4594	irs	0.4099	0.5117	0.8009	irs	0.4363	0.6607	0.6604	irs
27	Longido DC	0.2642	0.6421	0.4115	irs	0.2839	0.6772	0.4192	irs	0.2313	0.7938	0.2914	irs
28	Lushoto DC	0.0956	0.1986	0.4815	irs	0.1313	0.2689	0.4883	irs	0.1220	0.2598	0.4695	irs
29	Mafia DC	0.3257	1	0.3257	irs	0.5178	1	0.5178	irs	0.6110	1	0.6110	irs
30	Magu DC	0.1210	0.2915	0.4150	irs	0.1926	0.3451	0.5581	irs	0.1952	0.3846	0.5074	irs
31	Mbarali DC	0.1809	0.4007	0.4514	irs	0.1486	0.5100	0.2914	irs	0.1617	0.4766	0.3393	irs
32	Mbeya DC	0.1355	0.2642	0.5131	irs	0.1777	0.3525	0.5041	irs	0.1493	0.3918	0.3811	irs
33	Mbeya MC	1	1	1	crs	0.6225	0.6427	0.9685	irs	0.8611	0.8793	0.9792	drs
34	Mbozi DC	0.3249	0.4242	0.7659	irs	0.2324	0.3451	0.6735	irs	0.4143	0.4514	0.9177	irs
35	Misungwi DC	0.0452	0.2868	0.1577	irs	0.2129	0.4573	0.4656	irs	0.1363	0.5103	0.2671	irs
36	Mkinga DC	0.1676	0.4715	0.3555	irs	0.1945	0.5634	0.3452	irs	0.0981	0.8426	0.1165	irs
37	Mkuranga DC	0.2766	0.4842	0.5713	irs	0.2146	0.5301	0.4047	irs	0.2724	0.4585	0.5942	irs
38	Monduli DC	0.1031	0.3717	0.2773	irs	0.2571	0.4345	0.5917	irs	0.2294	0.6654	0.3447	irs
39	Morogoro DC	0.1003	0.2668	0.3758	irs	0.0875	0.2687	0.3257	irs	0.0649	0.4880	0.1330	irs
40	Morogoro MC	0.5123	0.5811	0.8815	irs	0.6975	0.7078	0.9854	irs	0.4575	0.5310	0.8616	irs
41	Moshi DC	0.0737	0.1634	0.4512	irs	0.1307	0.2452	0.5333	irs	0.1756	0.2740	0.6408	irs
42	Moshi MC	0.5062	0.6546	0.7734	irs	0.9414	1	0.9414	irs	1	1	1	crs
43	Mpwapwa DC	0.0697	0.2549	0.2735	irs	0.1304	0.3285	0.3970	irs	0.0776	0.3704	0.2094	irs
44	Muheza DC	0.1371	0.3381	0.4055	irs	0.2380	0.3736	0.6371	irs	0.2020	0.3983	0.5071	irs
45	Mvomero DC	1	1	1	crs	0.2591	0.3789	0.6838	irs	0.1033	0.3617	0.2855	irs
46	Mwanga DC	0.0850	0.3836	0.2215	irs	0.1025	0.3858	0.2656	irs	0.1953	0.4390	0.4448	irs
47	Ngorongoro DC	0.2765	0.5394	0.5126	irs	0.5960	0.6578	0.9062	irs	0.4389	1	0.4389	irs
48	Nzega DC	0.2004	0.3152	0.6358	irs	0.2189	0.3623	0.6041	irs	0.4645	0.6862	0.6769	irs
49	Pangani DC	0.9796	1	0.9796	irs	0.2034	1	0.2034	irs	0.2179	1	0.2179	irs
50	Rombo DC	0.1205	0.3103	0.3882	irs	0.1409	0.3622	0.3891	irs	0.1825	0.7719	0.2365	irs
51	Rufiji DC	0.4249	0.6396	0.6642	irs	0.4206	0.6827	0.6161	irs	0.2743	0.6154	0.4458	irs
52	Rungwe DC	0.2590	0.3690	0.7017	irs	0.2752	0.3516	0.7828	irs	0.1854	0.3748	0.4948	irs
53	Same DC	0.0687	0.2283	0.3009	irs	0.1861	0.3110	0.5986	irs	0.1448	0.3310	0.4376	irs
54	Sengerema DC	0.0947	0.1924	0.4923	irs	0.1986	0.3706	0.5359	irs	0.0907	0.3245	0.2795	irs
55	Siha DC	0.6790	1	0.6790	irs	1	1	1	crs	0.4535	0.6212	0.7301	irs
56	Sikonge DC	0.7442	1	0.7442	irs	0.7673	1	0.7673	irs	0.5214	1	0.5214	irs
57	Tabora MC	0.3306	0.4774	0.6925	irs	0.3732	0.4942	0.7551	irs	0.3741	0.5349	0.6994	irs
58	Tanga MC	0.7317	0.7934	0.9223	irs	0.8826	0.9360	0.9430	irs	0.7595	0.8781	0.8650	irs
59	Temeke MC	1	1	1	crs	1	1	1	crs	1	1	1	crs
60	Ukerewe DC	0.1486	0.3747	0.3966	irs	0.2252	0.4740	0.4752	irs	0.1720	0.6507	0.2644	irs
61	Ulanga DC	0.1245	0.3114	0.3998	irs	0.1275	0.3813	0.3343	irs	0.3922	0.7220	0.5433	irs
62	Urambo DC	0.6975	0.8375	0.8328	irs	1	1	1	crs	0.9845	1	0.9845	irs
63	Uyui / Tabora DC	0.2824	0.5333	0.5295	irs	0.5745	0.6827	0.8415	irs	0.3126	0.5636	0.5546	irs